

Investigating P&O Hybrid MPPT Algorithms Using PSO and GA for Solar PV Systems Under Varying Irradiances

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Abstract: The performance of solar PV systems is highly influenced by changing environmental conditions such as irradiance and temperature. Tracking the maximum power point (MPP), efficiently under these varying conditions is a major challenge. This study implements multiple Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms, including the traditional Perturb and Observe (P&O) method as well as hybrid approaches that combine P&O with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA). The performance of these algorithms is simulated under varying irradiance levels of 400, 600, 800, and 1000 W/m², providing a realistic evaluation of solar panel behavior under different environmental conditions. A novel approach is proposed in the paper by integrating evolutionary algorithms with traditional MPPT techniques to enhance tracking accuracy and system efficiency under dynamic environmental conditions. Increased short circuit current of 80 A, is considered with 10 parallel panels for higher the output power of Solar PV system. It is demonstrated by the study that a more reliable and efficient solution for solar power systems under moderate irradiance conditions is provided by hybrid MPPT techniques, especially P&O combined with PSO. Convergence time and oscillations are effectively reduced by the hybrid approaches, ensuring that operation close to the system's maximum potential is achieved with minimal performance loss. It is observed that P&O-PSO hybrid approach achieves 296 W, 444 W, 592 W, and 740 W power output for respective irradiances from 400 -1000 W/m²

Key Words: Renewable Energy, Hybrid Solar-Wind system, Machine Learning, Solar Load, Wind Torque, Neural Network, SVR, Ensemble Learning

1. Introduction

With the increasing penetration of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems into the global energy mix, maximizing energy extraction under varying environmental conditions has become critical. Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms [1], play a key role in ensuring optimal performance of solar PV systems by continuously adjusting operating points to harvest maximum power. Conventional MPPT techniques, such as Perturb and Observe (P&O) [2], [3], are extensively employed owing to their straightforward implementation and minimal computational requirements as illustrated in Figure 1. However, these methods exhibit notable problems and limitations, including slow convergence rates and persistent oscillations around the maximum power point. Furthermore, selecting an appropriate step size presents a significant challenge, as it directly influences the trade-off between tracking speed and stability. Under complex operating conditions, such as partial shading, the power-voltage characteristic curve may exhibit multiple local peaks, increasing the likelihood of the algorithm becoming trapped at a suboptimal point, thereby failing to identify the global maximum power point (MPP). To overcome these limitations, advanced optimization techniques like Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and hybrid approaches have been increasingly explored. Paper aimed to investigate P&O based hybrid optimization methods performance under different attendances. The abbreviations used are presented in Table 1 below.

Figure 1 Various Limitation and problems of conventional MPPT trackers for Solar PV system

Table 1 Abbreviation and Nomenclature of design parameters

Abbreviations		Abbreviations	
PV	Photo Voltaic	SVR	Support Vector Regression
		PWM	Pulse Width Modulation
RES	Renewable Energy System	RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
P&O	Perturb and Observe	GA	Genetic Algorithm
MPP	Maximum Power Point	MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks	DC	Direct Current
RBF	Radial Basis Function	AC	Analog Current
LR	Linear Regression	HOMER	Hybrid Optimization Model for Electrical Renewable energy
THD	Total Harmonic Distortion	NaN's	Not a Number

The study demonstrates that hybrid MPPT techniques, especially P&O combined with PSO, provide a more reliable and efficient solution for solar power systems under moderate irradiance conditions. The hybrid approaches effectively reduce convergence time and oscillations, ensuring that the system operates close to its maximum potential with minimal performance loss. The research incorporates time-series analysis to observe dynamic performance over time and uses a modular structure for easy comparison and modification of algorithms.

The MPPT refers to a system that utilizes specialized charge controllers to extract the highest possible power from solar modules under varying environmental conditions. The maximum power point (MPP) represents the specific operating point at which a solar module delivers its peak power output, ensuring optimal energy harvesting. Incorporating the hybrid approaches as a combination of conventional tracker and optimization methods may reduce oscillations, where adaptive strategies help stabilize operation around the MPP, minimizing energy loss due to fluctuations. Advanced methods are designed showcasing how optimization techniques maintain reliable performance amid rapid variations in irradiance, temperature, or load. Recent studies [1]-[6] have demonstrated that hybrid MPPT methods combining P&O with metaheuristic algorithms such as PSO and GA can significantly enhance tracking efficiency, improve response time, and maintain robustness under partially shaded or fluctuating irradiance conditions. This research focuses on designing and comparing P&O-based hybrid MPPT trackers integrated with PSO and GA to enhance the reliability and efficiency of solar PV systems across different environmental scenarios.

This research is aimed to demonstrate how an MPPT system increases the performance of any solar PV installation. Research is motivated to compare the performance of different MPPT based tracking mechanism to enhance the power output or performance of solar-based renewable energy systems. Primarily focuses on simulating and validating the model of a solar panel system and implementing various MPPT algorithms.

In this study, the performance of a MPPT controlled Solar PV system is analysed under different MPPT algorithm such as P&O, Incremental Conductance, PSO and GA methods. Validating the operating conditions using simulation-based evaluation. The block diagram and the schematic of proposed solar PV system is illustrated in Figure 2. A sequential work flow structure outline is given in Figure 2 (a). The steps involved in designing a hybrid optimization method for MPPT in solar energy systems. The process begins with simulation setup initialization where solar panel is modeled using a simplified linear approximation of the current-voltage relationship. the most common MPPT algorithm is P&O, uses power and voltage differentials to adjust the operating point. The solar irradiance variation is modeled as solar panel in the simulation. in the proposed method the model is then refined through *initializing optimization method* and

parameters. Finally, as a novel approach the hybrid models with *Optimization method as P&O-PSO*, and P&O-GA, integrates these components to enhance tracking accuracy and system efficiency under dynamic environmental conditions. Figure 2(b) illustrates the schematic operation of a tracker based Solar PV system integrated with a MPPT control algorithm. Solar irradiance from sun is converted into electrical energy by PV module, whose output voltage (V_{pv}) and current (I_{pv}) are continuously monitored. These measurements are fed into the MPPT control algorithm, which generates a Pulse Width Modulation (PWM) signal to dynamically adjust the operating point of the system. The Power Conditioning Unit receives this control signal and regulates the output voltage (V_{out}) delivered to the load, ensuring optimal energy extraction under varying environmental conditions. This configuration enhances system efficiency by maintaining operation at the maximum power point.

Figure 2 block diagram of basic MPPT based solar PV system tracker system

Contribution of Work

The key contributions of this work are:

- The testing and validating the Simulink model different Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms for solar PV systems.
- This study implements multiple Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms, including the traditional Perturb and Observe (P&O) and Incremental Conductance method as well as hybrid approaches that combine P&O with Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA).
- Detecting the impact of the different irradiance levels overperformance of MPPT using optimization methods.
- The paper proposes a novel approach by integrating evolutionary algorithms with traditional MPPT techniques to enhance tracking accuracy and system efficiency under dynamic environmental conditions. Simulating the power output of solar PV system V_s for a specified time period of 24 hours for various MPPT optimization method.

Overall paper has significantly contributed to focuses on testing and simulating various Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithms for solar PV panels to enhance system performance. The effectiveness of Perturb and Observe (P&O), Incremental Conductance, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and Genetic Algorithm (GA) based MPPT methods is investigated for designing efficient solar PV systems. The impact of varying irradiance levels from (400-100) is investigated on MPPT performance is analyzed using optimization techniques. The power output of the solar PV system is simulated over a 24-hour period for different MPPT algorithms, providing insights into their comparative efficiency and effectiveness under real-world conditions

2.0 Classifications of MPPT based Solar PV Systems

Different methodologies were designed to improve the performance of the MPPT tracker based solar PV systems in past. Figure 2 presents a structured classification of MPPT-based solar PV system designs, organized into three distinct algorithmic categories: Traditional, Intelligent, and Hybrid. the primarily MPPT-based solar PV system designs may be further broadly classified as Traditional, Intelligent, and hybrid methods. The Traditional algorithms branch includes the widely adopted Perturb and Observe (P&O) and Incremental Conductance (INC) methods, known for their simplicity and ease of implementation. The Intelligent Algorithms category features optimization approaches as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) and Genetic Algorithm (GA). Both of which leverage nature-inspired heuristics to enhance tracking efficiency and adaptability under dynamic environmental conditions. Finally, the Hybrid Algorithms sections showcases integrated approaches combination of these methods such as P&O-PSO and P&O-GA, which aim to combine the responsiveness of traditional methods with the optimization power of intelligent

techniques. This color-coded block diagram provides a clear visual taxonomy, facilitating comparative analysis and aiding in the selection of appropriate MPPT strategies for solar energy applications.

Figure 2 Classifications of MPPT based Solar PV systems modeling

3. Review of Litterature

in recent time many reserches have wrked to improve the effceicny of the solar PV systems specially those based on MPPT tracks. it is noted that efectivness of these methods higly vares under varying irrirdance condition. This section is aimed to reviewe literature emphesizing the evolution of MPPT algorithms from conventional rule-based methods to sophisticated hybrid and intelligent techniques, reflecting a growing emphasis on adaptability, efficiency, and real-time responsiveness in solar PV systems.

3.1 Treditonal MPPT Methods

Yousaf et al. [1] proposed a novel hybrid PSO-based MPPT algorithm that improves performance under varying irradiance and temperature. While effective, the method requires high computational resources and complex parameter tuning, which may limit its real-time applicability in low-cost embedded systems. Bruk et al. [2] simulated a large-scale 100 MW solar plant using PSO-P&O control, demonstrating scalability. Yet, the hybridization introduces algorithmic complexity and longer initialization times, which could affect responsiveness during rapid environmental changes. Majumder [3] compared P&O and PSO methods, noting that P&O is simple and fast but suffers from oscillations around the MPP and poor performance under rapidly changing conditions. PSO, while more accurate, is prone to premature convergence and requires careful selection of swarm parameters to avoid suboptimal tracking. Salman et al. [4] integrated machine learning and metaheuristics, offering predictive capabilities. However, such models demand large training datasets, offline learning, and significant memory, which may not be feasible for lightweight PV controllers.

Mitsuya and Meneses [5] evaluated ANN-PSO hybrids under partial shading, showing improved energy capture. Nonetheless, ANN-based systems are sensitive to training quality, and their black-box nature can hinder interpretability and fault diagnosis. Indumathi et al. [6] analyzed GA-PSO and GWO-PSO hybrids, which enhance global search capabilities. Still, these methods often exhibit slow convergence, parameter sensitivity, and difficulty in balancing exploration vs. exploitation, especially in real-time applications. Nagthane et al. [7] assessed P&O and INC algorithms in grid-connected systems with battery storage. While both are reliable and easy to implement, INC suffers from noise sensitivity in current and voltage measurements, and both methods struggle with tracking accuracy under partial shading. Lian and Andrian [8] proposed a modified INC with simulated annealing, which improves global search but introduces stochastic behavior and longer computation times, making it less suitable for fast-changing conditions. Amri et al. [9] developed a hybrid INC-PSO controller using XSG tools, demonstrating real-time simulation potential. However, the integration of PSO adds computational overhead, and the system may require hardware acceleration to meet real-time constraints. Sulthan et al. [10] introduced a two-stage hybrid MPPT algorithm with layered optimization. While modular and scalable, the approach involves multi-level control logic, which can be difficult to implement and debug, especially in distributed PV systems.

This analysis reveals that while hybrid and intelligent MPPT techniques offer superior performance, they often trade off simplicity, speed, and hardware compatibility. The choice of algorithm must therefore balance tracking precision, computational feasibility, and system constraints based on the target application.

3.2 Hybrid MPPT Methods

An extended review of recent literature reveals a growing emphasis on hybrid and intelligent MPPT techniques for solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, particularly under partial shading conditions (PSC), where conventional methods often fail to locate the global maximum power point (GMPP). Figueiredo and Aquino [11] proposed a hybrid PSO-P&O algorithm that combines the fast local tracking capability of Perturb and Observe (P&O) with the global search efficiency of Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). While this approach improves tracking accuracy under both uniform and shaded conditions, it introduces increased computational complexity and requires careful parameter tuning to avoid premature convergence or excessive oscillations. Mazumdar et al. [12] provided a comprehensive overview of MPPT methods, categorizing them into conventional, soft computing, and hybrid techniques. They highlighted that while AI-based methods such as PSO, GA, and ANN offer superior performance in dynamic environments, they demand high processing power and may suffer from slow convergence and instability if not properly configured.

Selvaraj et al. [13] reinforced these findings, noting that although hybrid methods outperform traditional algorithms in terms of energy extraction and response time, they often lack standardization and pose challenges in real-time implementation due to their algorithmic complexity and hardware dependency. Azad et al. [14] focused on the P&O algorithm under varying weather conditions, emphasizing its simplicity and ease of deployment. However, they acknowledged its limitations, including steady-state oscillations around the MPP and poor performance under rapidly changing irradiance or PSC.

Krishnaram et al. [15] introduced a novel hybrid MPPT technique integrated with a three-phase interleaved boost converter, demonstrating enhanced tracking efficiency and reduced ripple. Despite its benefits, the system's complexity and increased cost due to additional hardware components pose practical constraints. Chtita et al. [16] proposed a GWO-PSO hybrid algorithm that leverages Grey Wolf Optimization's exploration capabilities with PSO's exploitation strength, achieving improved convergence and robustness under PSC. Nevertheless, the method's stochastic nature and sensitivity to control parameters can affect consistency and scalability.

Dokala et al. [17] advanced this concept with a PSO-Improved GWO (I-GWO) hybrid, which further enhances tracking precision but suffers from increased algorithmic overhead and longer computation times, making it less suitable for low-power embedded systems. Hussaian Basha et al. [18] presented a novel hybrid MPPT controller design tailored for various PSC scenarios, integrating multiple optimization layers to improve adaptability and energy yield. While the controller demonstrated superior performance in simulations, its implementation complexity and reliance on high-speed processors limit its feasibility in cost-sensitive applications. Collectively, these studies underscore the trade-off between performance and practicality in MPPT algorithm design. Hybrid and intelligent methods offer significant gains in tracking accuracy and energy efficiency, especially under challenging conditions, but they often require advanced hardware, meticulous tuning, and robust validation to ensure reliability and scalability in real-world PV systems. The summary of the hybrid MPPT based recent solar PV systems is presented in the Table 2 along with limitations.

Table 2 Summary of hybrid MPPT based recent solar PV systems relevant review

Authors	Methodology	Optimization Used	Limitations
Kumar, Rajesh et al. [19] (2024)	Comparison of MPPT techniques in standalone PV systems	Fuzzy Logic Controller, P&O	Limited to standalone systems, may not address complex shading scenarios
Abo-Khalil, A.G. et al. [20] (2023)	Performance evaluation under partial shading	Hybrid SA-P&O	Partial shading addressed, but other disturbances not considered
Hussain, M.T. et al. [21] (2023)	Energy harvesting performance using ANN	Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)	Requires large dataset; may face overfitting in varied environments
Muhammad Zain Yousaf et al. [22] (2025)	MPPT optimization under varying conditions	Hybrid PSO	Performance highly dependent on parameter tuning

Zaghba, L. et al. [23] (2025)	Hybrid MPPT for energy harvesting in normal and shading conditions	Fuzzy Logic-PI optimized by PSO	Computational complexity and convergence time in real-time applications
Kumar, D. et al. [24] (2023)	Hybrid approach integrating machine learning	PSO-trained ML and Flying Squirrel Search	Trade-offs in convergence speed and computational requirements
Olfa Boubaker [25] (2023)	Review of MPPT techniques	AI-based optimization methods	Provides overview but lacks practical implementation details
Hayder, Wafa et al. [26] (2020)	Comparative study under partial shading	Improved PSO	Limited to specific shading scenarios; sensitivity to initialization
Ali, A. et al. [27] (2018)	GA-ANN optimization for PV control	Genetic Algorithm, ANN	Hybrid complexity may increase system cost and tuning effort
Mallat, M. et al. [28] (2023)	Off-grid MPPT using genetic optimization	GA	May require adaptive mechanisms for real-time disturbances
Indumathi, R. et al. [29] (2024)	Comparative analysis of hybrid algorithms	GA-PSO and GWO-PSO	Trade-offs between global and local search, sensitivity to parameters
Khairi, M.N.S. et al. [30] (2023)	MPPT design with PSO in PV systems	PSO	May not handle sudden irradiance fluctuations effectively
Yadav, A. et al. [31] (2025)	Assessment under dynamic shading conditions	Multiple MPPT algorithms	Challenges in robustness when conditions change rapidly

Table 2 summarizes the most common limitations and challenges observed across various MPPT techniques explored in recent research. Many studies highlight that while optimization algorithms such as PSO, GA, ANN, and hybrid approaches improve performance, they also introduce complexities related to parameter tuning, computational cost, and real-time adaptability. A frequent issue is the sensitivity of algorithms to initial conditions, which can affect convergence speed and stability, especially under rapidly changing environmental conditions like dynamic shading or partial shading. Several methods also require large datasets or extensive training, which increases the risk of overfitting and limits their general applicability across different operating scenarios. Furthermore, hybrid algorithms, though effective in enhancing directivity and gain, often involve trade-offs between global and local search capabilities, making them harder to implement without extensive customization. Other limitations include challenges in handling sudden irradiance fluctuations, increased computational effort, and the need for adaptive mechanisms to ensure robustness. These issues suggest that future hybrid MPPT designs should focus on improving algorithm adaptability, reducing complexity, and ensuring reliability under diverse environmental conditions while maintaining efficient power tracking. Addressing these limitations will be essential for developing next-generation solar PV systems with enhanced performance and broader practical deployment.

Therefore, this research is aimed to design and investigate the performance of hybrid combinations of traditional and optimization-based methods for improving the MPPT efficiency.

4. Proposed MPPT based Solar PV System Design

The study demonstrates how PSO and GA can improve tracking performance. Furthermore, time-series analysis is incorporated to observe dynamic performance over time, while the modular structure of the code ensures that each algorithm is implemented separately for easy comparison and modification. Overall, this framework offers a robust tool for optimizing solar energy systems by comparing and refining MPPT techniques under diverse conditions.

The mathematical modeling can be broken down into several stages:

1. **Solar Irradiance Modeling:** The solar irradiance is modeled as a time-varying function;

Where $G(t)$ is the irradiance in W/m^2 and t is time in seconds.

2. **Solar Panel Modeling:** A simplified linear model is used for the solar panel

Where i is the current, i_{sc} is the short circuit current, V is the voltage, and V_{oc} is the open circuit voltage, G is the irradiance, and k is the integer representing irradiance sample.

3. MPPT Algorithms:

In the proposed work four different MPPT tracker methods are tested and compared. The all four algorithms share common inputs at each time step as current solar irradiance $G(k)$, panel parameters β and previous operating point V_{k-1} . All these four methods run in parallel, each producing its own output and are modeled as shown in the Table 3.

Table 3 The Input and output parameters of four MPPT methods

Algorithm	Inputs	Output
Perturb & Observe (P&O)		
Incremental Conductance (λ)		
Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)	Particle positions and velocities	(best global position)
Genetic Algorithm (GA)	Population of voltage values	(best individual)

The Table 3 makes it clear that with the same aim of achieving MPPT all algorithms take the different set of inputs to optimize. For each of these four algorithm's output voltages, calculate the corresponding current and power:

Where x is P&O, PSO, and GA. The output power estimation is defined as

Store the power outputs for each algorithm at each time step as:

The outputs from each time step become inputs for the next iteration. each of these algorithms are described sequentially in this section.

- a) **Perturb and Observe (P&O):** This algorithm uses power and voltage differentials to adjust the operating point and is mathematically calculate power change as:

Figure 4 flow chart for the traditional P & O algorithm MPPT based Solar PV systems

Adjust voltage based on power and voltage changes. The flow chart as shown in Figure 4 described above represents the traditional P&O method, which is widely used for MPPT for the solar PV systems. In this algorithm, the changes in power and voltage between two consecutive iterations are calculated to determine the direction in which the operating voltage should be adjusted. If the change in power is positive, it indicates that the previous adjustment led to an increase in power output. In this case, if the change in voltage is also positive, the algorithm continues to increase the voltage by a fixed step size to further track the maximum power point.

As clear from Figure 4 that, if is negative, the voltage is decreased by the step size to maintain the direction of improvement. On the other hand, if the change in power is negative, it suggests that the previous adjustment resulted in reduced power. Therefore, the algorithm reverses the direction of voltage adjustment: if is positive, the voltage is decreased, whereas if is negative, the voltage is increased. This decision-making process allows the system to iteratively perturb the voltage and observe the resulting power change, thereby enabling it to converge toward the maximum power point. The P&O algorithm is simple to implement and computationally efficient, making it suitable for real-time applications; however, it may oscillate around the maximum point and its performance can be affected by rapidly changing environmental conditions.

- b) **Incremental Conductance ():** This method compares the instantaneous conductance () with the incremental conductance ().

Check if

If yes → MPP reached, keep $V(k+1)=V(k)$

Update $V(k-1)$ and $I(k-1)$,

Figure 5 flow chart for traditional Incremental Conductance MPPT based Solar PV systems

Adjust voltage based on the comparison. The Incremental Conductance MPPT flow chart is presented in Figure 5 is designed to accurately track the MPP point of a solar PV system by analyzing the relationship between changes in current and voltage. It begins by initializing key parameters such as voltage, current, step size, and a small tolerance value. At each iteration, the algorithm measures the current and voltage, then computes their incremental changes to determine how the power output is varying. By comparing the ratio of these changes to the negative of the instantaneous conductance, the algorithm decides whether the system has reached the maximum power point.

If the two values are equal within the specified tolerance, it concludes that the maximum power point is achieved and keeps the voltage unchanged. Otherwise, it adjusts the voltage in the direction that increases power output. Specifically, if the incremental conductance is greater than the negative instantaneous conductance, the voltage is increased, while it is decreased if the opposite condition holds true. The process is repeated by updating the previous measurements, allowing the algorithm to continuously adapt to changing conditions such as varying irradiance or temperature. Compared to simpler methods like P&O, the Incremental Conductance algorithm offers improved accuracy and faster convergence, making it suitable for systems where environmental fluctuations are frequent, though it requires precise measurement and accuracy is relatively low for varying conditions.

- c) **Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO):** This algorithm uses a population of particles with positions and velocities. Method have optimally update particle velocities as:

Update particle positions as:

Evaluate fitness functions as the power output for each particle in iterative manor

Figure 6 flow chart of proposed OSP based MPPT tracker

Figure 6 illustrates the flowchart for PSO based MPPT algorithm, commonly used in solar PV systems to dynamically extract optimal power under varying environmental conditions. The process begins with the initialization of particle parameters, including their positions and velocities, which represent potential solutions in the search space. The equations guide particles toward their personal best and the global best positions. The updated velocity is then used to compute the new position of each particle. The fitness function typically the power output of the solar panel and is evaluated for each particle to assess its effectiveness. The algorithm iteratively refines particle positions until a predefined iteration limit is reached, ensuring convergence toward the maximum power point. The flowchart clearly captures this iterative optimization loop, emphasizing the balance between exploration and exploitation in the PSO strategy.

d) Genetic Algorithm (GA):

Selection: Use roulette wheel selection based on fitness

Crossover:

Mutation: Add small random changes to some individuals

The GA-based MPPT system design flow chart is illustrated in Figure 7, follows a structured sequence inspired by evolutionary principles to optimize power extraction from photovoltaic systems. The process begins with the user's decision to implement genetic algorithm operations, initiating the algorithm with enthusiasm and readiness. Flow proceeds to the core stages of GA such as selection, crossover, and mutation. If selection is chosen, the system applies a Roulette Wheel Selection method, where individuals are probabilistically chosen based on fitness, then new individuals are generated by using the rule. This is followed by crossover, where arithmetic crossover combines parent solutions using the formula

Figure 7 flow chart for simple GA based MPPT Solar PV systems

This enhancing diversity and convergence. Mutation introduces random perturbations to maintain genetic variability, calculated as

This ensuring the algorithm avoids local optima. Each decision node in the flowchart guides the user through these operations, culminating in a final affirmation: “Great! Have fun with your algorithm,” emphasizing the adaptive and exploratory nature of GA in MPPT design. This flow ensures that the photovoltaic system dynamically adjusts to environmental changes, maximizing power output through intelligent, biologically inspired optimization.

e). Performance Evaluation

For each algorithm, calculate power output at each time step:

The input simulation parameters used for various optimized Hybrid MPPT model’s validation under test are given in Table 3.

Table 3 input simulation parameters used for various optimized Hybrid MPPT models validation

Parameter	Value / Range	Used In	Description
sim_time	8 seconds	All methods	Total simulation duration
dt	0.1 seconds	All methods	Time step for simulation
G_levels	[400, 600, 800, 1000] W/m ²	All methods	Irradiance levels for testing MPPT performance
V _{oc}	37 V	Solar model	Open-circuit voltage of the solar panel
I _{sc}	80 A	Solar model	Short-circuit current of the solar panel
V _{po}	20 V (initial)	P&O	Initial operating voltage for P&O algorithm
step_size	0.1 V	P&O	Voltage perturbation step for P&O updates

num_particles	10	PSO	Number of particles in the swarm
w	0.5	PSO	Inertia weight controlling velocity retention
c1, c2	1.5 each	PSO	Cognitive and social acceleration coefficients
window	± 1 V around V_{po}	PSO, GA	Search window centered on P&O voltage
Vmin, Vmax	$[0, V_{oc}]$	PSO, GA	Voltage bounds for particle or population search
population_size	20	GA	Number of individuals in the genetic population
num_generations	5	GA	Number of generations for GA evolution
mutation_rate	0.1	GA	Probability of mutation per individual
alpha	Random $[0,1]$	GA	Crossover blending factor between parents
r1, r2	Random $[0,1]$	PSO	Random factors for velocity update
positions, velocities	Initialized randomly	PSO	Particle states updated iteratively
fitness	Power output	PSO, GA	Evaluation metric for optimization ($P = V \times I$)

4 Proposed Hybrid Optimization based Design Flow

The proposed design flow for hybrid optimization based MPPT design methodologies is shown in Figure 8. The Solar PV system is tested against the various hybrid optimization methods combination with MPPT system. Then if the optimum performance is achieved then hybrid system is evaluated for achieving the MPP power point response for hybrid models outputs.

Figure 8 Design Flow chart of the proposed hybrid model testing

The Figure 8 illustrates the control flow of a hybrid MPPT algorithm designed to optimize solar PV system performance under varying environmental conditions. The flowchart begins with system initialization, followed by real-time measurement of PV voltage and current. These inputs feed into the primary MPPT algorithm typically P&O which attempts to track the maximum power point. A decision block criterion, such as rapid irradiance changes or oscillatory behavior are changed to determine whether the system should continue with the primary method or switch to a secondary MPPT technique, such as Incremental Conductance (. Depending on the outcome, the appropriate algorithm updates the duty cycle of the DC-DC converter to adjust operating voltage. The process includes a safety and fault logic stage to ensure system protection against overvoltage, overcurrent, or thermal anomalies. Finally, the loop returns to the measurement step, enabling continuous adaptation and tracking. This hybrid approach enhances tracking accuracy, improves dynamic response, and ensures robust operation across diverse solar conditions.

To design hybrid models the simulation methodology as shown in Figure 9 as block diagram, begin by selecting complementary algorithms or techniques to combine. Implement each component separately, then create an interface or wrapper class to manage interactions between them. Develop a decision-making mechanism to determine when to switch between models or how to weight their outputs. Implement data preprocessing and feature engineering steps to ensure compatibility across models. Design a unified input/output structure for seamless integration. Create evaluation metrics to assess the hybrid model's

performance. Implement error handling and logging for debugging. Finally, optimize the hybrid model through parameter tuning and iterative testing under various conditions.

Figure 9 Block Diagram of proposed Hybrid Model Design using PSO and GA

5. Expected Results

The results section has sequentially performed the various experiments and presented the results in three pas. the first pass has validated the impact of sinusoidal irradiance profile on various MPPT modes.

5.1 Experiment 1: Validation of sinusoidal Irradiance model for MPPT methods

This work focuses on the simulation and comparative analysis of various MPPT algorithms for solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, aimed at improving energy harvesting under fluctuating irradiance conditions. The study implements and evaluates four MPPT techniques as P&O, Incremental Conductance as traditional methods, and PSO, and GA based optimizations using a simplified solar panel model. The simulation runs over a 24-hour period, with irradiance modeled as a sinusoidal fluctuation to mimic realistic environmental changes. The PV panel’s open-circuit voltage and short-circuit current are used to calculate instantaneous power outputs for each algorithm. The P&O and methods rely on real-time incremental changes in voltage and current, while PSO and GA apply population-based optimization techniques to converge toward maximum power points. The initial model approximates the solar current as a linear function of irradiance and voltage, allowing for computational efficiency while capturing the essential dynamic behavior of the system. By comparing the performance of all four methods, this study aims to identify the algorithm that achieves the best trade-off between convergence speed, stability, and energy output for providing a robust foundation for optimizing solar PV systems in variable irradiance conditions.

Figure 10 Validation of the different MPPT models for sinusoidal solar irradiance profile for 24 h. The validation of various MPPT algorithms under a sinusoidal solar irradiance profile spanning 24 hours is presented in Figure 10. The graph highlights each method’s ability to track the MPP point as irradiance

fluctuates smoothly throughout the day. While all models exhibit periodic power output patterns, the inset zoom reveals subtle differences in tracking precision and response speed. In the zoomed portion of the graph, subtle differences between the algorithms' performances are highlighted.

The P&O method as in Figure 10 shows some oscillations near the peak power, indicating slower or less stable tracking under changing conditions. Incremental Conductance (I) performs slightly better but still exhibits minor fluctuations. Both PSO and GA algorithms demonstrate superior tracking behavior, with smoother curves and faster convergence toward the optimal power output. They are less affected by the rapid changes in irradiance and maintain higher efficiency throughout the simulation period.

Similarly comparison of the results for different irradiance profiles are given in the Figure 11. The input sinusoidal profile has already defined in eq. (1), the square irradiance model is mathematically defined as follows

Thus, the square irradiance alternates between:

Trapezoidal Wave Irradiance Profile

Figure 11 Results Validation of the different MPPT models for square and trapezoidal profiles

Results Validation of the different MPPT models for square and trapezoidal profiles are respectively shown in Figure 11 a) and Figure 11 b). It is clear from the Figures and highlighted zoomed comparison that although in close proximity but still PSO based MPPT method outperform over all.

5.2 Impact of Varying Irradiance on Output Power

The impact of the varying proposed irradiance model is compared as an experiment for the output power prediction using four MPPT models as Case 1. The irradiance is varied as . It is also clear from Figure 12 comparing the MPP performance for different MPPT methods against time at different irradiances, that as the irradiance increases the significant increase in output power is observed.

Figure 12(a) presents a comparative analysis of the performance of four distinct MPPT algorithms under a constant solar irradiance of 400 W/m². The results clearly demonstrate the varying efficiency and stability of each algorithm in tracking and maintaining the optimal power output of a solar PV system. Among the methods evaluated, although the Incremental Conductance algorithm exhibits stable performance with time but it's MPP achieved is less and around 29.4 only. The P&O algorithm begins near to similar power and it gradually shows longer time for convergence, but is prone to oscillations around the optimal point, indicating reduced tracking precision. The GA approach, although capable of exploring a wide solution space, presents significant variability in power output, with frequent deviations from the optimal level due to its stochastic nature. although GA perform better then the Incremental Conductance algorithm but highly fluctuating power output. In comparison PSO algorithm, while achieving faster convergence compared to P&O, suffers from slight instability and fluctuations, which may limit its reliability in practical applications. But the it achieves the maximum output power of around 29,6 W and thus outperforms. the

nature of all four modes remains same in all four cases of irradiances but significant boost in power output as MPP ranges is noticed.

Figure 12 Results of the predicted output power for the different irradiances

It is clear from the Figure 12 that as the irradiance increases from figure a)–d), the performance of I method decreases. and PSO based method out performs with maximum MPP. Figure 12(b) illustrates the dynamic performance of four MPPT algorithms under a constant irradiance level of 600 W/m². The maximum power achieved by I is 44.1 W, the GA demonstrate more power but highly fluctuating efficiency. The PSO and P&O methods outperforms with maximum of 44.4 W. But it is also observed that P&O method take nearly 1.5 s for reaching to maximum power level. Thus, overall PSO achieves maximum power output.

Similarly Figure 12(c) illustrates the dynamic performance under a constant irradiance level of 800 W/m². The maximum power achieved by I is 58.8 W, and PSO and P&O methods outperforms with maximum of around 59.2 W. The output power for maximum irradiance level of 1000 W/m² as in Figure 12(d) achieved 73.5 W MPP by I and PSO and P&O methods achieved the maximum power at around 74 W. Thus, it is required to improve the settling time of the P&O method using hybrid approaches.

5.3 Experiment 2: Optimized Hybrid MPPT Model Results

A ~37 V Voc module (about 60 cells in series) usually has ≈ 8–12 A at STC. As a modification and to map the real time existing scenarios to increase the power output corresponding to the 8 A of (for single cell assumption) in this work it is proposed using the 10 parallel cells unit for large scale power production equivalent to real time 300 W scenarios. An experimental comparison of the impact of the proposed dynamic range of irradiance model on output power prediction has been conducted using hybrid MPPT models as Case 2, with irradiance levels varied as $G(k) = [400, 600, 800, 1000]$ W/m². Figure 13 compares standard P&O method with hybrid combination of the P&O-PSO and P&O-GA algorithms. Figure 13(a) illustrates the comparative results of hybrid MPPT methods at a irradiance of 400 W/m². It is

clearly noted that the hybrid approaches enhance the tracking efficiency and stability of the power output compared to the standard P&O algorithm. The P&O + PSO method achieves the fastest convergence, reaching the maximum power point within approximately 1 second and maintaining a steady output close to the optimal value.

Figure 13 Results of Hybrid optimization models based predicted output power for different irradiances

It is clear from Figure 13 that the P&O + GA approach also improves convergence but slightly fluctuating around the peak value, settling after approximately 2.5 seconds. The conventional P&O algorithm takes longer to reach the MPP and shows noticeable oscillations. Figure 13 a) proposed hybrid model simulating P&O with increase start at around 294 W and achieves a MPP of around 296 W, but with evident fluctuations around this value. While hybrid model P&O+PSO reaches a peak power of around 296 W and stabilizes quickly, indicating superior convergence and tracking accuracy. The combination of P&O + GA also attains a peak near 296 W, though it exhibits slightly more variability than the PSO-based hybrid method. From the Figure 13 b) for 600 W/m² irradiance the MPP output is increased and ranging from 441 to 444 W. But the wider time range makes it clear that convergence rate also decreased at this irradiance range.

Similarly, from the Figure 13 c) showing results for 800 W/m² irradiance the MPP output is increased and ranging from 587 to 592 W. And it is noted that at higher range the convergence rate is also faster. For the maximum irradiance profile of 1000 W/m² during day MPP power efficiency increases to 734.5 to 740 W as shown in the Figure 13 d). In order to further justify the results the Box plots corresponding to Figure 13 are plotted in the Figure 14 at different irradiances representing the Interquartile Range (IQR) is a statistical measure that captures the spread of the middle 50% of a dataset.

It is clear from Figure 14 a) that at an irradiance level of 400 W/m², the P&O method shows the widest interquartile range (IQR), with Q1 at 294.0 W and Q3 at 295.0 W, yielding an IQR of 1.0 W. Its median power output is 294.5 W, and the full range spans from 293.5 W to 295.5 W, indicating greater variability

and less stable tracking. The P&O + GA method also performs better than the baseline, with an IQR of 0.8 W ($Q1 = 294.6$ W, $Q3 = 295.4$ W) and a median of 295.0 W. It ranges from 294.0 W to 295.7 W suggests moderate stability and output enhancement. The P&O + PSO method demonstrates the most consistent performance, with a narrower IQR of 0.6 W ($Q1 = 295.3$ W, $Q3 = 295.9$ W) and a higher median of 295.7 W. It ranges from 294.5 W to 296.0 W reflects both improved convergence and reduced fluctuation.

Figure 14 Results of Hybrid optimization models IQR ranges for different irradiances

Figure 14(b) illustrates the comparative performance of MPPT methods for 600 W/m² irradiance using IQR analysis. The P&O algorithm exhibits the widest IQR of 1.6 W, highlighting significant variability in power output and less stable tracking. In contrast, P&O + PSO achieves the tightest IQR of 1.0 W, indicating superior consistency and convergence. P&O + GA demonstrates intermediate behavior. Figure 14(c) presents the IQR-based comparison of MPPT methods at 800 W/m², with P&O method shows the widest IQR of 1.4, while P&O + PSO achieves a tighter IQR of 1.0 W, with a higher median of 588.8 W. but for this case specific P&O-GA demonstrates the most stable performance, with the highest median of 589.2 W and the narrowest IQR of 1.0 W. Finally it is clear from Figure 14(d) that that at 1000 w/m² P&O has an IQR of 2.6 W. The both hybrid methods as P&O-PSO and P&O-GA shows a tighter IQR of 1.4 W. But P&O-GA may have slimly higher median value of 739.0 W. Since it has more fluctuating nature with time, thus still P&O-PSO is preferred over P&O-GA.

Overall, it is clear from Figure 14 that, traditional P&O shows the widest spread and lowest median, indicating more fluctuation and less stable tracking. The hybrid combination of P&O+PSO has the tightest IQR and highest median, suggesting fast convergence and consistent performance. While The P&O+GA performs better than P&O but slightly less stable than PSO.

These results demonstrate that hybrid MPPT techniques, especially P&O combined with PSO, provide a more reliable and efficient solution for solar power systems under moderate irradiance conditions. The hybrid approaches effectively reduce convergence time and oscillations, ensuring that the system operates close to its maximum potential with minimal performance loss.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

This research has provided a thorough analysis of MPPT algorithms for solar PV systems under a range of irradiance conditions. By comparing traditional methods such as P&O and Incremental Conductance () with advanced techniques including PSO and GA based Optimizations, and their hybrid combinations. The research has demonstrated the significant benefits of integrating hybrid evolutionary algorithms with traditional approaches. The hybrid methods, particularly P&O-PSO, showed superior performance in terms of faster convergence, greater stability, higher power output, and reduced oscillations around the maximum power point. These hybrid models proved adaptable to different irradiance profiles, making them suitable for practical solar energy applications.

- The paper performed simulations in three phases in the first phase the sinusoidal, square and trapezoidal irradiance profiles are used for comparing performance of different basic MPPT methods. It is concluded that PSO optimization based MPPT method achieves the higher MPP in all cases.
- In second phase initial validation Case 1 with the Incremental Conductance () achieves a MPP of 29.4 W while PSO outperforms other methods with an MPP of 29.6 W for minimum irradiance of 400 W/m².
- Finally for the case 2 in the hybrid model, P&O with increased starts at around 294 W and achieves an MPP of about 296 W. And the hybrid P&O+PSO hybrid reaches and stabilizes quickly at a peak power of 296 W for minimum irradiance of 400 ,

At all tested irradiance levels (400, 600, 800, and 1000 W/m²), the PSO and P&O methods consistently achieved higher MPPs compared to method. Hybrid models, such as P&O with PSO or GA, also demonstrated competitive MPP performance, with the P&O+PSO hybrid noted for its rapid stabilization. IQR analysis revealed that the P&O method generally exhibited wider performance variations (larger IQRs) across different irradiances, whereas the hybrid methods consistently displayed narrower IQRs, indicating greater stability. These numerical results consistently demonstrate that the hybrid MPPT methods, particularly P&O+PSO, outperform traditional methods in terms of power output, convergence speed, and stability across various irradiance levels.

6.1 Future Work

In future it is expected to test the systems under various real-world scenarios, including rapidly changing irradiance and partial shading conditions. Partial shading scenarios and how the hybrid algorithms respond to non-uniform irradiance across panels. Another scope for future is implementing and comparing other nature-inspired optimization algorithms

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